

Supplementary Methodological Report

Protocol for Grey Literature Review on Corporate RAG Systems

Supplementary Material to the Main Manuscript

February 16, 2026

Abstract

Abstract. This document serves as the formal replication protocol for the Grey Literature Review (GLR) presented in the main manuscript. It details the search strategy, screening criteria, data extraction schema, and synthesis methods used to identify and categorize corporate Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) use cases.

1 Rationale for Grey Literature

We conducted a Grey Literature Review (GLR) to address the limitations of traditional academic indexing regarding emerging technologies. Two primary factors drove this decision:

1. **Practical Implementation vs. Theory:** Our research focuses on the *practical* implementation of corporate RAG systems. Valuable industry use cases are frequently documented in non-academic channels (e.g., engineering blogs, white papers, case studies) rather than peer-reviewed journals.
2. **Timeliness:** RAG technology is in an early adoption phase. Academic publication cycles often lag behind rapid industrial iterations. A GLR ensures the capture of the most current trends and innovations.

To ensure rigor, this review adapts the search and selection guidelines for software engineering grey literature proposed by Garousi et al. (2019).

2 Search Strategy

Pilot Search & Engine Selection

A pilot search was conducted to define the search strategy and validate potential sources. We performed comparative searches across Google, Bing, and DuckDuckGo. Based on result analysis, **Google** was selected as the sole engine for this study due to:

- **Precision:** Preliminary assessment indicated Google yielded the highest precision for corporate technical reports. Bing and DuckDuckGo results frequently overlapped with Google or returned generic consumer content.
- **Geolocation Filtering:** Google's region-specific indexing allowed us to leverage the authors' linguistic competencies, capturing adoption patterns in both English (US) and German (DACH) markets.

Keyword Formulation

The pilot phase validated the efficacy of search strings. To avoid over-constraining results, strings were kept concise (2–3 words) and anchored by the term "RAG". The

final query set included: (i) *Corporate RAG*, (ii) *RAG use cases*, (iii) *RAG application*, (iv) *RAG framework*, and (v) *RAG implementation*.

Execution

The main search involved automated scraping of the Google result ranking. We employed an **effort-bound termination strategy**, stopping data collection after the first five result pages (approx. 50 hits per query), as relevance dropped beyond this point. Paid advertisements were programmatically omitted. In total, 10 distinct searches were performed (5 strings × 2 regions), yielding an initial pool of **457 web links**.

3 Selection and Screening Process

The source selection process followed the flow illustrated in Figure 1.

Deduplication (Identification)

Web links were aggregated into a master dataset. An automated deduplication script compared URLs and normalized titles, reducing the initial 457 links to 248 duplicates and leaving **209 unique records** for screening.

Screening Criteria

We applied a high-level binary assessment (Include/Exclude) to the 209 unique records. Sources were removed ($n = 149$) if they failed any of the following checks:

1. **Accessibility:** Page loads correctly and is not behind a hard paywall.
2. **Language:** Content is in English or German.
3. **Relevance:** Title/Abstract explicitly mentions RAG or generative AI in a corporate context.

Eligibility Assessment

The remaining 60 sources underwent full review. At this stage, 37 sources were excluded for being: (i) purely theoretical (no specific use case), (ii) broken links upon second visit, or (iii) generic marketing content lacking technical detail. This resulted in a final set of **23 core sources**.

4 Data Extraction and Feature Coding

Targeted Snowballing

As illustrated in Figure 1, we expanded our dataset through a targeted tracing approach rather than exhaustive backward snowballing. When reviewing the 23 core

Figure 1: Flow diagram of methodology process.

sources, we specifically looked for mentions of practical RAG implementations.

If a source briefly highlighted a use case and provided a hyperlink (e.g., to a technical blog or vendor report), we followed this reference. Furthermore, where a specific company or implementation was mentioned without a direct hyperlink, we conducted supplementary ad-hoc web searches to locate the primary source (e.g., the referenced company’s official engineering blog). This pragmatic expansion yielded an additional **65 external references**, allowing us to document use cases that were otherwise only partially described.

5 Data Synthesis

Tooling & Annotation Protocol

We utilized Zotero for bibliographic management and initial review. To systematize the process, we applied a semantic color-coding scheme directly within source documents:

- **Magenta (Concrete Use Case):** Text segments describing implemented, real-world RAG systems.
- **Green (Abstract Use Case):** Theoretical mentions or potential applications without evidence of implementation.
- **Blue (Contextual Metadata):** Information regarding the industry, domain, or specific organization.
- **Orange (Qualitative Factors):** Explicitly stated challenges, limitations, or observed benefits.

Extraction and Enrichment

Coded segments were transferred to a structured extraction matrix (Google Sheets). We performed a data enrichment step: since grey literature often omits formal classification data, we consulted publicly available business information to map companies to the **Global Industry Classification Standard (GICS)**.

Data Synthesis Strategy

We employed an inductive approach to categorize use cases. We initially attempted to follow existing classifications but shifted to a strategy focusing on high-level business outcomes:

1. **Open Coding:** Specific behaviors/goals were extracted.
2. **Archotyping:** Codes were grouped into ten Use Case Archetypes.
3. **Functional Clustering:** Archetypes were synthesized into four overarching Functional Clusters.

6 Automated Feature Extraction

To analyze qualitative dimensions (Challenges and Benefits) across all 76 use cases, we developed a custom automated extraction pipeline using the OpenAI API, specifically leveraging the native multimodal capabilities of **GPT-5**.

Extraction Pipeline Architecture

The pipeline executed a one-shot extraction task:

1. **Direct Document Processing:** We forwarded raw PDF documents directly to the model’s multimodal context window. This preserved document layout, ensuring complex structures (tables, sidebars) were accurately interpreted.
2. **Structured Output Enforcement:** We utilized the Pydantic library to define rigid output schemas, constraining the model to return valid JSON.
3. **Attribute Extraction:** The model extracted specific attributes, including verbatim *Context Quotes* for verification and *Severity* assessments.

Categorization Strategy

Challenges (Deductive Mapping): We anchored the model to a fixed taxonomy mapping findings into nine categories: (i) *Data Quality*, (ii) *Retrieval Accuracy*, (iii) *Generation Quality*, (iv) *Latency & Performance*, (v) *Cost & Resource Efficiency*, (vi) *Security & Compliance*, (vii) *Integration & Infrastructure*, (viii) *User Adoption*, and (ix) *Other*.

Benefits (Semi-Supervised Discovery): We adopted a flexible approach. While provided with a baseline set of benefits, the model was permitted to output raw descriptions for novel findings, which were subsequently processed to establish new categories such as *Tone Adaptation* and *Multilingual Capabilities*.